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Perceptions and Teachers' Experiences of Distance Learning Towards Challenges in the New Normal Education

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Abstract

Objective: This research study explored the experiences and perceptions of distance learning towards readiness and the challenges teachers face in implementing Distance Learning in the New Normal. **Methods:** An adopted survey questionnaire was used to collect the challenges faced by 140 teacher respondents during the COVID-19 pandemic for the SY 2021-2022. The data on lived experiences, perceptions, and challenges met by teachers was fielded online via Google Forms. **Findings:** Data revealed the challenges met in module preparation were highly evident with a mean of 3.46, the distribution of module garnered a 3.49 mean as highly evident, and retrieval of module got a mean of 3.01 interpreted as moderately evident. Formative assessment results are moderately evident with a mean of 3.38, while summative assessment is highly evident with a mean of 3.41. In the implementation of distance learning home visitation, remediation was a moderate and highly evident challenge with a mean average of 3.33 and 3.47 respectively. However, challenges met by teachers in new normal education were moderate to highly evident. The teachers expressed their readiness to switch to distance learning education; they felt hampered due to a lack of facilities, equipment, and capacity building for distance learning education. The results showed no budget in the modular setup of education, learners are not available at home. Sometimes learners did not seriously answer the module and have unrealistic answers about their work on the module. **Novelty:** Many challenges emerge inadequate knowledge, time management, reliability, and validity of learners' performance are difficult to identify, only a few or very low retrieval of modules of the learners, and performance of learners was low from preparation to retrieval of modules. Advanced further tests were done on a bigger sample to validate other challenges of distance learning modalities in new normal education.

Keywords: Perception; New normal education; Distance learning; Teachers experiences

1 Introduction

COVID-19 is not just causing health crises around the world, but it is also affecting all spheres of life, including the field of education. Educators resorted to online platforms to reach out to students, webinars became a temporary classroom, parents were called for monitoring at home, and students were deprived of social interaction among peers. The WHO advised educators and students to conduct alternative learning due to the COVID-19 outbreak to mitigate school cancellation of classes by providing a resource list of the World Bank's Ed-tech teams to provide some online materials that can be used during the pandemic. The program aims to elevate the loss of learning and provide remote learning opportunities while schools are closed. Furthermore, the mandate provides guiding principles and delivery of online classes and approaches to be given by stakeholders like teachers and parents (World Bank, 2020a). Various countries around the world, Colombia, Italy, Japan, Poland, etc., including the Philippines, responded to the call of WHO through their respective Ministry of Education. Various educational platforms were utilized like YouTube, a learning management system (LMS), a digital library, internet streaming or broadcast, repositories like Open Educational Resources (REA), and the like based on their availability in a particular country. Higher education makes use of Zoom and Google Hangouts, while teachers were encouraged to take advantage of various websites, such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and Google Forms. EdTech Hub, UNESCO Education Alliance, Learning Keeps Going (U.S. consortium), Inter-Agency Network for Education in Emergencies (INEE), Commonwealth of Learning, and many others (World Bank, 2020b). Responding to the call of WHO, the Department of Education (DepEd, Philippines), created a series of DepEd Memorandum (DM) No. 15, 21, 23, 31, and 34 in the first quarter of 2020 entitled "Creation of a Task Force for the Management of Department of Education Response to Novel Coronavirus Acute Respiratory Disease (2019-nCoV ARD)" (Department of Education, 2020a). The DepEd, Philippines, also created a learning website called DepEd Commons catering to Alternative Learning School (ALS) students, Out-of-School-Youth (OSYA), and regular learners from Kindergarten to Grade 8. The uneventful happenings due to COVID-19 forcibly implemented distance learning in all levels of instruction aided mostly by available technology. Distance Learning (DL) is not new. It has been part of the learning process for decades now. The last 50 years have seen huge growth worldwide in the provision of education at all levels. Distance learning, also called distance education, e-learning, and online learning, form of education in which the main elements include the physical separation of teachers and students during instruction and the use of various technologies to facilitate student-teacher and student-student communication. Distance learning traditionally has focused on non-traditional students, such as full-time workers, military personnel, and non-residents or individuals in remote regions who are unable to attend classroom lectures. With COVID-19, all learning endeavors are now in distance learning as the modality. As this pandemic is slated to exist until the preventive vaccine is discovered, it is essential to know how the educators who are the prime facilitators of education adjusted to this transition and what experiences they faced while adapting to this transition as their preparedness for the coming times. Considering teachers' experiences and perceptions, the findings will be used as a basis for policy implementation. This action research aimed to explore the teachers' perceptions and experiences in the implementation of distance learning at Dolores District. It aims to explore their lived experiences which can be used as a springboard for a policy proposal that will better the implementation of distance learning.

1.1 Research Questions

This action research study focused on analyzing the lived experiences of teachers and their perceptions of the implementation of distance learning at Dolores District amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of teachers in the implementation of distance learning during the COVID-19?
2. What are the perceptions of teachers in the implementation of distance learning during COVID-19?
3. Based on the results of the survey questionnaire and focus interview, what suggestions and recommendations may be offered for a smooth implementation of distance learning?

1.2 Significance of the Study

As this pandemic is estimated to exist until the preventive vaccine is discovered, it is necessary to know how educators, who are the prime facilitators of education, adjusted to this transition and what challenges they faced while adapting to this transition as their preparedness for the coming times. This study aimed to find the factors and determinants that can facilitate a smooth implementation of distance learning in the Philippines. Specifically, this research is vital to:

Policy Makers. The conclusions of this research endeavor could aid them in devising suitable mediations that best fit the current scenario and be able to not only deliver but improve excellence in education as well despite this educational upheaval.

Teachers/Educators. The results of this scientific endeavor may be vital in implementing solutions that will enable teachers to maximize their roles as teachers and optimize results where they are happy teaching in distance learning.

Parents. The findings of this study will help parents deal with the learning process. Inputs from policies out of the recommendations will improve the implementation of distance learning

Students. Most importantly, results from this academic undertaking may be of great benefit to students. It could give them drive on how to handle their struggles and influence them to study even harder to overcome their learning gaps in Science during the pandemic.

Future Researchers. The findings of this study will serve as a basis for other researchers to embark on a similar study.

1.3 Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study was conducted at Dolores District by selected secondary teachers in complete enumeration. The challenges they are experiencing in the implementation of distance learning during the pandemic were solicited via Google Forms. Only teachers from the district were forwarded with the link to the online form this only explored the challenges in the district. The research was conducted in the second quarter of SY 2021-2022.

2 Review of Related Literature

2.1 The Distance Learning System

Although the focus today lies on distance learning in higher education enabled by the present digital technologies, considering distance learning provides perspectives on the historical rationales of such education and suggestions on alternative forms. Distance learning was historically largely organized to address the needs of adult learners who could not take years away from their professional lives for full-time studies at a university. The cost of education was significant for such learners, and for adult learners with families, moving to another town was not always an option. Other reasons for distance education were the need to serve distant rural locations, and in other cases this format was motivated by colonial projects, aiming to gain influence over populations across the world. The beginning of distance learning as a form of continuous higher education was established in the mid-nineteenth century. Forms of distance education have become more varied with modern-day technological developments, starting with education by correspondence; then education on radio and television; the use of audio and audiovisual media; the use of the educational phone, interactive video, and the educational computer; to the internet and the progress achieved in the field of education from a distance. The introduction of digital libraries and information systems helped the development of education from its collective form (within the classroom) to the individualization of education and has highlighted the importance of distance learning. According to Jawda et al. ⁽¹⁾ in 2016, distance learning is considered a new method of education for so many people, as it adopts methods that are different from those used in the traditional education system. There are many methods used to convey information to learners, instead of relying on one source, as is the case in traditional education e.g., flexibility in acceptance and learning, as the learner can receive his education anywhere, and expenditure savings, as this type of education is less expensive than other education systems⁽¹⁾. Among the major disadvantages of ICT-mediated distance learning is that the distance learning system lacks direct interaction and communication between the teacher and the learner, which is currently deficient in providing humanitarian and social expression and cannot provide real expression. The flexibility shown by this system and its acceptance of low grades as a basis in the system is a weak point when compared to the traditional system⁽¹⁾. Moreover, Jawda et al. added several obstacles that hinder distance learning, the need for training in internet use by teachers and students, and the lack of technological infrastructure at universities. Other important points are those related to students where they are living such as the need for access to safe internet and high-quality-speed internet and specifications, which leads to quick access to data and information. Hence, this leads to secure exchange between the network user and internet service provider specifically during electronic exams (online exams or tests). In recent decades an increased number of educational organizations have decided to plan and implement a distance learning platform. It is also seen as an opportunity for a more efficient organization and management of higher education institutions (HEIs) (OECD, 2016: 103). Conventional classroom-based institutions face an important question about how to develop the distance learning initiative. The main aim of educational organizations is to remain competitive by keeping their scientific standards high or improving their offered services while keeping the required investment low (OECD, 2012): 26-27. As a result, they rush to provide technology-enhanced learning to their students, using distance learning platforms. The implementation of distance learning requires a rather high initial cost, which is sometimes hidden behind the rapidly changing technology, making the effort more expensive than face-to-face (European Commission, High-Level Group on the Modernization of Higher Education, 2014). Conventional educational institutes should engage academics and academic planners in the process of designing their distance

learning strategy, for the implementing technology to be effective and to achieve the targets set (OECD, *Innovating Education and Educating for Innovation: The Power of Digital Technologies and Skills*, 2016):85; (Mora Rodriguez, 2013). Traditional face-to-face educational institutes that plan to implement distance learning initiatives require concrete strategic thinking to integrate educational programs based on technology in their established learning methods and traditions (Oliver, 2010). The approach to implement and promote distance learning should follow a step-by-step model, to embed different opinions, smooth reactions, and develop the required educational content and methodologies. Distance learning cannot be followed successfully without strategic planning (OECD, 2016: 110). The literature review proves that a road map for distance learning planners in higher education is rather mandatory for successful implementation. Distance learning is a discrete and comprehensible field of education that is focused on new methods of realizing the educational process while at the same time maintaining a pedagogical philosophy⁽²⁾. Distance learning should not be considered a teaching mode or method and only. Relevant studies have shown that distance learning planning is focused on budget and staffing issues and not on its critical pedagogical issues and that is the reason why the greatest challenge for education institutions that move towards distance learning is to adopt a singular vision, policies, and procedures for implementation.

2.2 Distance Learning Technologies

The use of technology to assist in the processing and dissemination of knowledge is not new. Over the last 50 years, rapid technological advances in computer and communication technologies facilitated the development of alternative educational methods and supporting technological tools (Stošić, 2015). The available educational methods applied to distance learning are divided into two basic categories: synchronous and asynchronous learning⁽³⁾. Synchronous learning is defined as course delivery with all participants present at the same time even in different places. It simulates classroom teaching methods in which participants are not physically located in the same place but are geographically dispersed. It is also executed upon a predefined schedule, which must be followed by all the participants. Asynchronous learning is a more flexible method of learning, where learners have access to course materials on their schedule from virtually any place. Learners are not required to attend at the same time (Farhad, 2017). The various technologies used in distance learning can be roughly divided into four categories: text, audio (voice), computer (data), and video (Ion, Vespan, & Ută, 2012). For example, statistical research on the use of electronic communication in distance learning identified the following types of applied telecommunication media in such programs: telephone, fax, audio-conference, electronic mail, and access to databases⁽⁴⁾. Printed material may serve as the primary source of instruction, or it may play a supplemental role and serve as a primary source, distant students might use a textbook and read various units on a specific timetable⁽⁵⁾. Other technologies, such as e-mail, could then be used to ask questions and send assignments back to the teacher. As a supplement to instruction, text materials may take the form of worksheets or study guides that are used in conjunction with video or voice technologies. It is important to note that the supplemental text material may be disseminated via regular mail or regular web pages. This type of information is quite easy to print. There are many advantages and disadvantages to incorporating printed material in a distance learning course. Some advantages of printed materials are extremely portable (can be used in any location), have a high comfort level (most students are very comfortable using print materials to learn), are cost-effective (can be created and duplicated with little expense), readily available (many distance learning courses can take advantage of existing textbooks, thus saving the time and expense of creating new materials). Printed educational material lacks interaction. Printed tutorials or handouts do not offer interactivity, making learning a rather unpleasant experience. The lack of electronic educational content created the need for additional technologies to support the learning process.

2.3 Distance Learning in Education Driven by COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic led educators to online education readiness. Modular printed modality may have been the most chosen modality, but undeniably, the use of the internet and technology prevails in most learning transactions which necessitates the teachers to use communication technologies like Facebook Messenger, Gmail, and social media to do follow-up and strengthening connectedness between teacher and learners. With these, it is necessary to look into considerations of how well are teachers doing in distance learning. According to Phan & Dang (2017)⁽⁶⁾, factors such as training, attitude, technical competence, time constraints, pedagogy, and methodology were among the major distance learning education elements. A study conducted by Ventayin (2018) on the readiness of DepEd Teachers for online teaching, showed that despite the limited experience in distance education such as technical skills, time management, knowledge, and attitude in online education, they were still able to cope with the trends in distance learning. Moreover, readiness and satisfaction levels were also found among prospective teachers in other countries like Turkey and Thailand in terms of web-based education⁽⁷⁾. Further, in the study on the response from 205 online faculty of higher institutions in the United States in terms of readiness, attitude, and ability to

teach online in terms of course design, course communication, time management, and technical aspects most of the responses were rated high (Martin, Budhrani & Wang, 2019). Furthermore, another study on distance education readiness found that 90% of the total special education and preschool teachers surveyed got motivated to implement distance education despite having diverse students, lack of specialists, being home-schooled, under long medical treatment, attending short stay with groups or family and private school⁽⁸⁾. Likewise, in another study, higher education mentors showed a positive attitude and motivation to teach university students special needs like hearing and visually impaired despite the risks and challenges in learning materials, pedagogy, monitoring, implementation, and psychological understanding⁽⁹⁾. Collectively, the literature suggests that there are many things that we need to know about distance learning. Its implementation may not be new, but doing it in full swing means bigger collateral damage at hand which happens to be the gap that this research proposal is trying to solve.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design. A type of research design aimed to describe and examine the relationships or associations between variables without manipulating or intervening in the study. It focused on observing and measuring variables as they naturally occur and exploring how they are related to each other. The descriptive survey questionnaire was chosen for its ability to systematically collect and analyze data regarding the characteristics, perceptions, and experiences of participants. An adapted survey questionnaire was used to collect the challenges faced by teachers of Dolores District during the COVID-19 pandemic for the SY 2021-2022.

3.2 Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at Dolores District during the second grading period of the School Year 2021-2022. Questionnaires were fielded online only to teachers of Dolores District. Complete enumeration was employed and selected secondary teachers were asked to answer the online survey instrument via Google Forms.

3.3 Respondents of the Study

This study involved selected secondary teachers from all schools in the district. Complete enumeration of the total number of teachers used the fishbowl sampling technique due to the manageable number of identified respondents. The Google Form link was posted on the official messenger group chat of the school district after all safety protocols and permits were acquired. The district principal announced that teachers needed to access the link and answer the survey with a 100% response rate. Moreover, the researcher followed necessary health protocols in the collection of data.

3.4 Research Instruments

The instrument used in this study was an adopted survey questionnaire that explored the challenges of teachers and their lived experiences in distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. As the research survey questionnaire is already standardized, there was no need to validate the said survey questionnaire material. The research instrument is a self-report questionnaire based on experiences faced by teachers in terms of challenges through the implementation of distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

3.5 Data Collection Method

This study started on the second week of December 2021 as part of the second grading School Year 2021-2022. Selected secondary teachers of Dolores District answered the survey online via Google Form attaining a one hundred percent (100%) retrieval rate for the survey. Responses were downloaded as MS Excel files and used for interpretation and analysis. Before the fielding of the survey questionnaire, a permit was acquired from the District Principal-In-Charge and School Principals of Dolores District through communication letters stating the request to conduct the online survey and the promise to adhere to the confidentiality protocols. After all targeted participants had responded to the online survey form, the researchers disabled the 'collecting responses' feature of the Google Form to hold the integrity of the data.

3.6 Measurement of Variables

The questionnaire which was used to gather information about the challenges met by elementary teachers on distance learning during this pandemic was measured using the following:

Scale	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Meaning
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Highly Evident	Manifest that challenges met are very highly evident
4	3.40 – 4.19	Highly Evident	Manifest that challenges met are highly evident
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Evident	Manifest that challenges met are evident
2	1.80 – 2.59	Less Evident	Manifest that challenges met are less evident
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Evident	Manifest that challenges met are not evident

3.7 Analysis of Data

For the translation of data into meaningful information, descriptive statistics was used to analyze and gather data using frequency, and mean percentages, and presented in tables and graphs.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

This study followed the appropriate research ethics guidelines. Consent from the respondents was provided, and a permit was ensured to use their given data. The participants were assured that these data were kept confidential and could not be used in legal actions against them.

4 Result and Discussion

The struggles and challenges experienced by teachers in the implementation of distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic include the following: struggles and challenges in preparation, distribution, and retrieval of modules including the type of assessment used in the modular print implementation as a modality.

As displayed in Table 1, teachers responded that the problems they face in module preparation including inadequate knowledge of module writing, budget for materials in module writing problem, references for the module or learning activity sheets are not available and time used are highly evident problems with a mean average of 3.46. In line with this, the two most prominent categories were the pedagogy of modules illustrating their centrality in teachers’ experiences. Both positive and negative experiences in online distance teaching were the preparation of modules and teachers’ attitudes toward technology integration in education faced by a teacher during the pandemic⁽¹⁰⁾. Furthermore, the teachers have manifested their awareness of distance learning education experiences and perceptions towards modular preparation⁽¹¹⁾.

Table 1. Challenges faced by teachers via distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of Module Preparation

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Inadequate knowledge of module writing	3.42	Highly Evident
Budget for materials in module writing is a problem	3.47	Highly Evident
References for the module or learning activity sheets are not available	3.47	Highly Evident
Time is also a problem	3.47	Highly Evident
Average	3.46	Highly Evident

In Table 2 the problems encountered by teachers on module distribution yielded a highly evident interpretation that teachers of Dolores district did experience a highly evident problem in this aspect. As seen in Table 2, with a weighted mean average of 3.49, it can be observed that the issue of module preparation was a highly evident problem. The importance of readiness and the cognitive reaction to changes in the teachers’ perception of the development of their “teacher expertise” highlights the need for continuous training of teachers in computer use and technology literacy in the distribution of modules⁽¹²⁾.

In Table 3 during the implementation of module retrieval as a learning modality of distance learning, teachers of Dolores district responded that the indicators evaluated on module retrieval as problems are moderately evident with a mean average of 3.01. Similarly, according to Koet and Aziz (2021)⁽¹³⁾, the same findings also reveal that a variety of factors influence teachers’ and students’ impressions of distant learning, including the availability of facilities and networks, ICT abilities, administrative

Table 2. Challenges faced by teachers via distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of Module Distribution

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Learners are not available at home sometimes	3.68	Highly Evident
Some families are not observing safety measures to avoid COVID-19	3.58	Highly Evident
Modules or learning activity sheets are not enough	3.26	Highly Evident
It takes time to distribute the modules/LAS	3.42	Highly Evident
Average	3.49	Highly Evident

and learning assistance, learning preferences, and learning environment by understanding how distance learning is perceived in retrieval of module.

Table 3. Challenges faced by teachers via distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of Module Retrieval

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Most of the time modules/LAS are not answered	3.37	Moderately Evident
Some modules/LAS are torn and returned messy	3.00	Moderately Evident
The retrieval rate is very low	2.84	Moderately Evident
Some parents are not cooperative.	3.0	Moderately Evident
Average	3.01	Moderately Evident

As for the formative assessment during the implementation of distance learning in the district due to the COVID-19 pandemic, results show that the challenges in the administration of formative assessment were moderately evident with a weighted mean of 3.28. The modular approach to distance learning in education for the formative assessment has specific measures such as adopting flexible learning to be considered for those who lack access to an internet connection and other resources⁽¹⁴⁾.

Table 4. Challenges faced by teachers via distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of Formative Assessment

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Activity sheets are unanswered	2.95	Moderately Evident
Answers are sometimes not realistic	3.20	Moderately Evident
It is hard to identify which one is the actual answer of the learners	3.74	Highly Evident
Only a few activity sheets are answered	3.21	Moderately Evident
Average	3.28	Moderately Evident

As to summative assessment, however, it can be gleaned from Table 5 that the challenges in the administration of summative assessment were interpreted as a highly evident issue with a weighted mean of 3.41.

Table 5. Challenges faced by teachers via distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of Summative Assessment

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Learners find it difficult to gather	3.21	Moderately Evident
Very-low performance is recorded	3.53	Highly Evident
Some learners are not serious	3.68	Highly Evident
Unrealistic grading is sometimes done	3.20	Moderately Evident
Average	3.41	Highly Evident

When asked about the challenges they experienced during the implementation of remediation in terms of the COVID-19 pandemic, secondary teachers of Dolores District in terms of home visitation interpreted as moderately evident with a mean of 3.33. The distance learning and instructional methods during the COVID-19 pandemic students reported negative experiences of distance learning such as lack of social interaction and positive experiences such as time and location flexibility⁽¹⁵⁾.

When asked about the challenges experienced during the implementation of remediation in times of the COVID-19 pandemic the teachers of Dolores district in terms of Remediation interpreted as Highly evident with a mean of 3.47.

Table 6. Challenges faced by teachers via distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of Home Visitation

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Parents are sometimes uncooperative	3.00	Moderately Evident
Some learners are indifferent	3.16	Moderately Evident
No-class homes in some residences or houses	3.58	Highly Evident
Some children are not present at home	3.58	Highly Evident
Average	3.33	Moderately Evident

Challenges faced by teachers via distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of formative assessment, summative assessment, home visitation, and remediation. During these challenging times, teachers have to re-think an intervention and innovations to deliver their lessons rather than face-to-face encounters. The school plays a vital role in this journey since they are the ones who provide training and seminars for the teachers to be equipped with the skills and knowledge in distance learning education⁽¹⁶⁾. Distance learning education could build access for learners in secondary education of Dolores District. However, distance learning education might be hard to execute in new normal education, yet it can boost technology utilization⁽¹⁷⁾. Lastly, schools must know how to plan, implement, and evaluate a school activity or program like distance learning education to ensure its success in quality education to the new normal.

Table 7. Challenges faced by teachers via distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of Remediation

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Uninterested learners are evident	3.42	Highly Evident
Materials are inadequate	3.37	Highly Evident
Sometimes not done because of time constraint	3.42	Highly Evident
It's challenging to identify learners who will undergo remediation because of unrealistic answers in their modules/LAS	3.68	Highly Evident
Average	3.47	Highly Evident

5 Conclusions

Face-to-face learning engagement of students and teachers within the school has been suspended due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This pandemic has paved the way for the implementation of modular distance learning as an urgent response to ensure continuity of education. with the implementation of distance learning, Dolores district opted to implement modular print as a learning modality. unwanted by many, the challenges that emerged from this implementation have caused havoc to teachers, learners, and even parents. this study was pushed through with the key purpose of finding out the challenges encountered by teachers and their implications on the academic performance of learners of Dolores district. after a survey that solicited the challenges met by teachers in the implementation of modular print as a modality of distance learning, the following are the conclusions of this research:

They showed varied characteristics of the challenges met by teachers in terms of module preparation, distribution, retrieval, formative assessment, summative assessment, home visitation, and remediation the result was moderate and highly evident. The teachers expressed their readiness to switch to distance learning education; however, they felt hampered due to a lack of facilities, equipment, and capacity building for distance learning education. The results showed no budget in the modular setup of education, learners are not available at home. Sometimes learners do not seriously answer the module and have unrealistic answers about their work on the module.

However, teachers have a significant experience and perception of their readiness for distance learning education. Overall, the teaching community is mentally prepared to adapt to new and innovative ways of imparting knowledge, provided their institutions will support them in the new normal education.

The experiences and perception of educators on the risk posed by the COVID-19 pandemic and the implementation of the enhanced community quarantine dictates a call for action for an alternative mode of learning. The adaptation of various online education and modular forms of alternative delivery modes of education during ECQ is a good indicator of good practices in the teaching and learning process.

To provide education during the pandemic, it is recommended by this study that the schools should opt for distance learning for the coming school year along with providing teachers' capability building for distance learning education. Likewise, investing

in the facilities and equipment needed for distance learning is an excellent idea to enhance the institution's capability to deliver distance learning to the students.

The delivery of printed materials through the local courier should also be considered. It will be beneficial to harness various media to feature academic lessons in audio, printed, and visual like TV and radio with schedule and monitoring based on conducive learning time.

Furthermore, continued monitoring and evaluation of distance learning education would be a great help to enhance the system of delivering quality education in the new normal setting.

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